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Influence of Parental Education Programmes on Child Abuse and Neglect of Early Childhood Children in Ibadan Metropolis, Oyo State

¹Moyinoluwa Grace OWOJORI, (PhD) & ²Jemimah A.I. ABIOYE

^{1&2}Department of Arts and Social Science Education, Lead City University, Ibadan

moyinowojori@gmail.com, owojori.moyinoluwa@lcu.edu.ng

abioyejai@gmail.com, abioye.jemimah1795@fcesoyo.edu.ng

Abstract

Child abuse and neglect are major global challenges with profound and lasting consequences for individuals, families, and communities. This study investigated the effectiveness of parental education programmes as a determinant for child abuse reduction in Ibadan Metropolis, Nigeria. Two purposes and two research questions guided the study. A descriptive survey research design was employed with a population comprising all parents in Ibadan Metropolis, Nigeria. Random sampling technique was used to select the sample of 200 parents. Data was collected using an online survey questionnaire. The instrument received validation from specialists in Early Childhood Education, and its reliability was confirmed using Cronbach's Alpha, resulting in a coefficient of 0.81. Data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation to examine relationships. The findings revealed that child abuse is reduced with parents who have had one form of education programme on child abuse or another. Based on the findings, the study recommended, among others, that parents should be encouraged to actively participate in parental education programmes, as it will be an eye-opener for them. Also, government and organisations are implored to allocate more funds to support the development, implementation, and expansion of evidence-based parental education programmes.

Keywords: Child abuse, Child neglect, Parental education programme, Early Childhood Children

Introduction

Child abuse and neglect remain a serious concern in many communities, especially in urban areas where stress, poverty, and lack of awareness contribute to harmful parenting practices. Many parents unknowingly engage in abusive behaviour due to limited knowledge about child development, proper discipline, and emotional support. Educating parents through structured programmes offers a proactive approach to address this issue. These programmes aim to equip parents and caregivers with skills in positive parenting, stress management and child rights awareness. When effectively implemented, they can significantly reduce harmful practices and promote safer home environments, ultimately contributing to a decline in child abuse and neglect.

Child abuse and neglect are significant global issues with long-term effects on individuals, families, and communities (World Health Organization, 2020). It includes physical, emotional, and sexual abuse, as well as neglect, leading to serious physical, psychological, and emotional harm. Affected children often face challenges such as poor health, low self-esteem, academic struggles, and long-term trauma. These impacts can persist into adulthood and strain social system. Despite awareness, it remains a widespread concern, highlighting the urgent need for effective prevention and intervention strategies to combat child maltreatment.

Child maltreatment encompasses a range of behaviours that endanger a child's well-being, including physical abuse, inform of child battery, beatings that leave scars on the child, child been subjected to hunger for days that may prone the child to stealing, sexual abuse, emotional abuse and neglect (U.S. Department of Health & Human Services, 2024). National incidence studies consistently highlight the widespread nature of the problem. For example, in the United States, the Children's Bureau reports that millions of children are involved in child protective services investigations annually (U.S. Department of Health & Human Services, 2021). Worldwide, it is estimated that a substantial proportion of adult's report experiencing some form of child maltreatment before the age of 18 (Stoltenborgh et al, 2013). Child abuse and neglect can have serious and lasting effects on individuals, influencing nearly all areas of their lives. In addition, research has shown that child maltreatment is a strong predictor of later involvement in the criminal justice system, substance abuse, and engagement in risky sexual behaviors during adulthood (Widom, et al, 2016)

Child abuse and neglect are serious issues that raise so much concern through a wide range of risk and protective factors operating at the individual, family, and community levels. Among the risk factors, parental issues such as substance abuse, mental health disorders like depression and anxiety, a history of being abused, limited education, and inadequate parenting

skills are common contributors (Afifi et al., 2011). Child-specific factors, including young age, disabilities, and behavioral challenges, also elevate the risk of abuse (Claussen & Crnic, 2010). For instance, children four years old and those with special needs, including developmental disabilities and chronic health conditions, are more vulnerable to maltreatment (Centers for Disease Control & Prevention, 2024).

According to Kiersz (2024), family-related risk factors often encompass poverty, unemployment, domestic violence, social isolation, and single-parent households. Economic hardship has been linked to child abuse and neglect. On a broader level, community conditions such as limited access to support services, exposure to violence, and societal norms that tolerate violence against children continue to elevate the risk of child maltreatment. Research has shown that neighbourhoods with high rates of social isolation and elevated crime levels often lack essential support infrastructure, increasing the likelihood of abuse and neglect (CDC, 2024; Ross & Tolan, 2021)

Conversely, protective factors play a critical role in buffering children from the negative outcomes associated with these risks and in promoting resilience. Positive parental attributes such as effective parenting skills, secure attachments, higher education levels, and strong social support systems contribute significantly to child well-being (Thompson, 2016). Children may exhibit characteristics that help protect them from harm, including having high self-esteem, effective problem-solving skills and healthy relationships with peers. In addition, families that are closely bonded, communicate openly and have access to essential resources such as financial support, counseling, or education are less likely to experience or perpetrate abuse. Also, communities that offer safe living conditions, access to high-quality childcare, healthcare services and strong social connections provide a supportive environment that helps safeguard families at risk.

One effective strategy to mitigate the risk of abuse and neglect is to promote healthy family dynamics in implementation of parental education programmes. These programmes are designed to enhance parenting skills, expand parental knowledge and cultivate positive parent-child relationships which could be accessed through radio programmes, television programmes, religious centres or social media platforms. Rooted in well-established theoretical frameworks, such as Ecological systems theory and Cognitive behavioural theory these interventions recognize the pivotal role of parenting in shaping child development. Parental education programmes are structured interventions aimed at enhancing parenting skills, expanding parental knowledge and fostering healthy parent-child relationships. While these programmes differ in content, format and the populations they target, they generally strive to address known risk factors for child maltreatment while strengthening protective factors (Sanders, 2012). Core components commonly include instruction on positive discipline techniques such as reinforcement and time-out, the development of effective communication and problem-solving skills, provision of information regarding child development and behavior, support for managing parental stress and coping mechanisms and efforts to build social support networks.

Ecological Systems Theory views child development as occurring within a dynamic system of interacting influences, ranging from the family to the broader community and culture, making it essential for parental education programmes to target multiple layers of influence to achieve meaningful change (Bronfenbrenner & Morris, 2006). This theory emphasizes the interplay between the child and their environment, as it emphasizes considering multiple layers of influence to promote healthy development. It consists of 5 systems, which are, Microsystem, Mesosystem, Exosystem, Macrosystem, and Chronosystem. Invariably, parental education programmes should target multiple layers of influence to achieve meaningful change, which will result in promoting meaningful change and support healthy development in children.

Furthermore, Cognitive Behavioral Theory is another theory that emphasizes the interconnection between thoughts, emotions, and behaviours, and parental education programmes grounded in this theory aim to help parents identify and replace harmful thought patterns and behaviours that may contribute to child maltreatment (Kendall, 2000). These principles form the foundation for effective parental education programmes. It emphasizes the interconnection between thoughts, emotions, and behaviors. According to this theory, an individual's thoughts and cognitive processes play a crucial role in shaping emotions and behaviours. Additionally, CBT is a problem-focused approach that aims to help individuals identify and replace harmful thought patterns and behaviours with more adaptive ones. Parental education programs grounded in CBT aim to help parents identify and replace harmful thought patterns and behaviors that may contribute to child maltreatment. These programmes focus on teaching parents' skills such as cognitive restructuring, emotional regulation, behavioural skills training, and learning effective parenting skills (such as communication, problem-solving, and discipline techniques (Webster-Stratton, 2018). Research has shown that CBT-based parental education programs can be effective in reducing child maltreatment and improving parenting practices.

Empirical studies and systematic reviews have provided strong evidence supporting the effectiveness of these programmes in reducing instances of child abuse and neglect. Numerous meta-analyses affirm that parental education programmes positively influence both parenting practices and child outcomes (Gaffney, et al, 2019; Mikton et al., 2017; CDC, 2024). Specifically, these interventions have been found to improve parenting abilities and knowledge, with increased use of

constructive discipline and a decrease in harsh or punitive methods. They also contribute to reduced rates of child maltreatment, including fewer reported cases of physical abuse and neglect. Additionally, these programmes have shown benefits in improving children's behaviour and emotional health, decreasing parental stress and depressive symptoms, and enhancing overall parent-child interactions.

Nonetheless, the success of such programmes is not uniform and can vary based on factors such as the design of the intervention, how faithfully it is implemented, and the specific characteristics of the population being served (Knapp et al., 2011). Some programmes yield more significant outcomes than others, and certain demographic groups may respond better to specific approaches. Despite these variations, the overarching goal remains consistent in preventing child maltreatment.

Statement of the Problem

Child abuse and neglect are huge problems affecting millions of children worldwide, with severe consequences for their physical, emotional, and psychological well-being. Studies revealed that the prevalence of child abuse and neglect is alarming in Ibadan. It has also been identified that parenting practices and parental education are critical factors in preventing child abuse and neglect. However, many parents lack the necessary skills and knowledge to provide a safe and nurturing environment for their children.

Despite the importance of parental education in preventing child abuse and neglect, we have little research on the effectiveness of parental education programmes in Ibadan. Research evidence further showed that many parental education programmes is on providing information on child health and nutrition, rather than addressing the root cause of child abuse and neglect. Therefore, this study investigated the influence of parental education programmes in reducing child abuse and neglect in Ibadan metropolis.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are to:

- i. examine the influence of parenting education programmes on child abuse and neglect in Ibadan, Oyo State.
- ii. examine the extent to which parental education programmes that influence the risk factors for child abuse and neglect at the individual, family, and community levels.

Research Questions

- i. How do parental education programmes on child abuse and neglect in Ibadan, Oyo State?
- ii. To what extent do parental education programmes contribute to the reduction of risk factors for child maltreatment at the individual, family, and community levels?

Methodology

This study employed a **descriptive survey research design** to examine the influence of parental education programmes in reducing child abuse and neglect in Ibadan, Oyo State. This design was selected to collect data from a sample of parents, allowing for a detailed understanding of their experiences and perceptions regarding parental education. The study's population consisted of all parents in Ibadan Metropolis. Random sampling was used to select a sample of 200 adults who acknowledged that they are parents who had either participated in or been exposed to parental education programmes at one point or another. This sampling method was chosen to ensure that participants had relevant experience or knowledge of the program under investigation.

The **research instrument** used for data collection was an **online survey questionnaire** titled "Parental Education and Child Abuse Reduction Questionnaire (PECARQ)". The questionnaire was developed by the researcher to capture the necessary data related to the research objectives. It consisted of both closed-ended and 4 Likert scale questions (Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree and Strongly Disagree) designed to gather quantitative data on the participants' experiences, perceptions and the impact of parental education programmes on their parenting skills. The validity of the instrument was ensured through content validation. The questionnaire was reviewed by experts in Early Childhood Education and related fields to assess its relevance, clarity, and alignment with the research objectives. These experts provided feedback and suggestions for improving the instrument's content, ensuring that the questions effectively addressed the study's research questions.

The instrument's reliability was evaluated using Cronbach's Alpha, a well-established method for assessing internal consistency. The reliability was determined through the administration of the instrument on parents who are not under the scope of the study and coefficient 0.81 was obtained, demonstrating a high level of consistency and reliability in the

participants' responses. This score indicates that the instrument is sufficiently reliable for data collection in the study. Data analyses involved descriptive statistics, including frequency counts, percentages, means, and standard deviations.

Results and discussion

Analysis of demographic characteristic

Table 1: Gender distribution of participants' demographic variables.

Variable	Gender Category (N=200)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	90	45
	Female	110	55
Total		200	100.0

Results in Table 1 summarize the gender distribution among 200 participants in the study. 90 representing 45% of the respondents were male while 110 of them representing 55% were females, showing that majority of the respondents were female.

Table 2: Age distribution of participants' demographic variables.

S/No	Age (in Years)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1.	18-25	60	30
2.	26-35	100	50
3.	36-45	30	15
4.	46-55	10	5
5.	56 and above	0	0
Total		200	100.0

Results in Table 2 showed that the greatest proportion of the respondents (50%) were between the age brackets of 26 to 35 years. This was followed successively by those who were 18 to 25 years old (30%), 36 to 45 years old (15%), and 56 years and above were (0%). This shows that this study covered the targeted respondents it was meant for.

Table 3: Educational Level distribution of participants' demographic variables.

S/No	Educational Level	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1.	Postgraduate	80	40
2.	B.A./B.Ed./B.SC/B.Tech	60	30
3.	HND	30	15
4.	NCE / OND	30	15
5.	Others	None	0
Total		200	100.0

Table 4.3 revealed that postgraduate were 80 (40%) B.A./B.Ed./B.SC/B.Tech were 60 (30%) HND were 171 (34.2%), NCE / OND were 30 (15%) while others were none (0.0%) of the total respondent. This showed that respondents on postgraduate had the highest percentage. Indicating that the participants likely have higher awareness and access to parental education programmes, which could enhance programme influence

Section B

This section provided answers to the research questions

Research question 1: How do parental education programmes on child abuse and neglect in Ibadan, Oyo State?

Table 1: Summary of Result showing Mean and Standard Deviation to describe the Influence of Parental Education Programmes on Child abuse and neglect

<i>Statement</i>	<i>Strongly Agree</i>	<i>Agree</i>	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Strongly Disagree</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>
<i>I have learned effective discipline strategies.</i>	40%	35%	5%	5%	4.05	0.85
<i>I have gained knowledge about child development.</i>	50%	40%	3%	2%	4.25	0.75
<i>I feel more confident in my parenting abilities.</i>	45%	40%	3%	2%	4.10	0.80

The results indicate that the mean ratings for all assessed items were above 4.00 on a 5-point scale, indicating strong agreement among participants regarding the influence of the programme. The highest mean score was recorded for gaining knowledge about child development (M = 4.25, SD = 0.75), followed by increased confidence in parenting abilities (M = 4.10, SD = 0.80) and learning effective discipline strategies (M = 4.05, SD = 0.85). The relatively low standard deviations across these items suggest that respondents were consistent in their positive views. These findings demonstrate that the programme influenced parents' knowledge, confidence, and disciplinary approaches, which are crucial in shaping healthy child-rearing practices and reducing risks of abuse and neglect.

Research question 2: To what extent do parental education programmes contribute to the reduction of risk factors for child maltreatment at the individual, family, and community levels?

Table 2: Summary of Result showing Mean and Standard Deviation to describe Parental education programmes that influence the incidence of child abuse and neglect risk factors

Risk Factor	Before Programme	After Programme	Percentage Reduction
Parental use of harsh punishment	30%	10%	66.7%
Parental stress and depression	40%	20%	50%
Lack of communication with children	35%	15%	57.1%

The finding shows a significant reduction in specific risk factors for child abuse and neglect following programme participation. The most notable decline was observed in parental use of harsh punishment, which decreased from 30% to 10%, representing a 66.7% reduction. Similarly, lack of communication with children dropped from 35% to 15% (57.1% reduction), while parental stress and depression reduced from 40% to 20% (50% reduction). These reductions indicate that the programme positively influenced parenting behaviours and emotional well-being, thereby strengthening family dynamics.

Discussion of findings

The findings of this study revealed that parental education programmes significantly improved parenting skills and knowledge. Respondents reported learning effective discipline strategies, gaining knowledge about child development, and feeling more confident in their parenting abilities. These findings are consistent with Sanders (2012), who emphasized that well-designed parental education programmes enhance positive parenting practices such as the use of reinforcement over punitive discipline. Similarly, Gaffney, Tunnard, and Minnis (2019) confirmed that such programmes contribute to improved parenting behavior and decision-making, particularly when tailored to the needs of the population. These improvements are crucial for promoting healthy parent-child interactions, a key factor in child development. Mikton et al. (2017) also noted that education programmes aimed at parents significantly increase their knowledge of developmental milestones, leading to more appropriate responses to children's behaviours.

Another significant finding was that participants reported a reduction in risk factors associated with child maltreatment after participating in the education programmes. This includes a decreased use of harsh punishment, reduced parental stress and depression, and improved communication with children. These outcomes align with MacMillan (2009), who found that parents participating in structured education programmes showed a marked decline in abusive behaviors. Furthermore,

Knapp et al. (2011) highlighted that the effectiveness of these programmes is often visible through improvements in the emotional climate of the home, reduction in parental frustration, and greater use of non-violent discipline methods. The stress reduction and improved coping mechanisms can be linked to the component of parental education that focuses on stress management and social support, as also described by Sanders (2012).

Summary of findings

The study found that participants significantly enhanced their understanding of child development, positive discipline strategies, and communication techniques with their children after attending parental education programmes. This improvement in parenting skills contributed to more informed and confident parenting practices. Findings indicated that parental education programmes helped reduce key risk factors such as parental stress, harsh disciplinary practices, and limited knowledge of child behavior. Parents reported adopting healthier coping strategies and improved emotional regulation.

Conclusion

Parental education programmes represent a promising approach to preventing child abuse and neglect. By improving parenting skills, increasing parental knowledge, and fostering positive parent-child relationships, these programmes have the potential to reduce child abuse rates and promote healthy child development. However, further research is needed to address gaps in the literature and optimize the design, implementation, and evaluation of parental education programs. Parenting for positive change should also be researched, using culturally adapted programmes with effects in parenting practices and child welfare. A comprehensive approach that combines parental education with other prevention strategies, such as early childhood intervention and community-based support services, is likely to be most effective in reducing child abuse and neglect and creating safer and healthier environments for children. Notably, studies have shown that well-designed parenting programmes can reduce the risk of child maltreatment by up to 30%, highlighting their substantial potential as part of broader prevention efforts.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Parents are encouraged to actively participate in parental education programmes as it will serve as an eye-opener for them.
2. Governments and organizations should allocate increased funding to support the development, implementation, and expansion of evidence-based parental education programmes
3. Parental education programmes should be made readily accessible to all families, particularly those identified as being at higher risk of child abuse and neglect. Strategies to enhance accessibility include offering programmes in diverse community settings, both rural and urban, at schools, healthcare clinics, community centers, and so on.
4. Parental education programmes should be developed and implemented through campaigns by both Non-Governmental Organizations and the Government. These initiatives must be customized to address the unique needs and cultural contexts of the families they aim to support.
5. Educators and policymakers should design programmes grounded in established theoretical frameworks and incorporate evidence-based practices shown to be effective in promoting positive parenting, reducing risk factors, and preventing child maltreatment.
6. Parental education programmes should be integrated with other existing services and systems, such as healthcare, social services, and early childhood education programmes. This integrated approach can provide families with comprehensive support and enhance the overall effectiveness of prevention efforts.
7. Successful prevention efforts require strong community engagement and collaboration among various stakeholders, including parents, educators, healthcare providers, social workers, law enforcement, and community leaders. In consequence, partnership should be highly encouraged.
8. Religious organizations, social media, and mass media should not relent in the enlightenment campaign on the need for parents to be educated on child abuse and neglect.

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